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ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: INPUT FOR SCHOOL
IMPROVEMENT PLAN**

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Examining the Relationship Between Student Self-Assessment Practices and Academic Performance: Input for School Improvement Plan

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between the academic performance of Senior High School graduates in a rural Philippine town and their self-evaluation methods. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design and included a sample of thirty individuals who had recently finished their schooling. The study employed academic records, questionnaires, and performance reports as methods of data gathering. The study employed Barry Zimmerman's Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) Theory, which emphasizes the need of self-monitoring, self-reflection, and goal-setting in achieving successful learning outcomes. A clear correlation was discovered between students' academic performance and their engagement in self-assessment methods. In order to develop metacognitive ability, the research concluded that it is crucial to actively engage in education, conduct self-assessment, and aim for exceptional academic performance. The study's flaws mostly stemmed from its limited scope, which only targeted a certain secondary educational institution fresh graduate. Nevertheless, it stressed the importance of doing further research in other educational contexts to verify the accuracy of the findings.

Keywords: *Education, Academic Performance, Learning Strategies, School Improvement Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Student self-assessment occurs when learners assess their performance. Self-assessment will be beneficial as it can develop students' learning skills for professional competence and make them aware of and more responsible for their learning processes (Calinescu, 2023; Gerodias, 2024). Self-assessment helps students develop metacognitive skills and become more self-directed learners. Through reflection and evaluation, students gain a deeper understanding of their abilities and enhance critical thinking skills.

Students' self-assessment practices in the classrooms increase their interest and motivation, support them to be more proficient in their work, promote their selfregulated learning, and improve their academic success and performance (Oscarson, 2013; van Loon & Roebers, 2017; Vasu et al., 2020). Thus, students will be more proactive learners with accurate selfassessments (Boud, 2019). Even though self-assessment is an essential component of effective learning (Black & William, 1998), self-assessment is not applied commonly in many classrooms (Brown & Harris, 2013).

Self-assessment has a direct impact on students' achievement (Shatri et al., 2022). However, if this self-assessment is not accurate, then students may set themselves inappropriate learning goals and mismanage their learning efforts, which will lead to lower performance both for them and for their institution (Kun, 2019). Students exposed to self-assessment training can also improve their academic performance (Karaman, 2021). Self-regulation mediates the relationship between students' academic motivation and academic performance (Ariani, 2016):

The relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic performance can be understood from the perspective that students with a high sense of efficacy can accept more challenging tasks, have a high ability to organize their time, have increased persistence in the face of obstacles, show lower anxiety levels, show flexibility in the use of learning strategies and have a high ability to adapt with different educational environments (Abdelmotaleb et al., 2020).

Framework

This study is grounded in Barry Zimmerman's Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) Theory, which is instrumental in understanding how students can enhance their academic performance through self-assessment practices. SRL theory posits that effective learning involves a cyclical process of forethought, performance, and self-reflection, where learners set goals, monitor their progress, and reflect on outcomes. This framework supports the research by highlighting the importance of self-assessment for students to become more aware of their learning strategies and performance, ultimately leading to improved academic results. By applying SRL theory, the study can better explore how self-assessment practices influence students' academic achievements, providing valuable insights for educators and learners alike. The study aims to understand how these variables impact academic outcomes. Gender, grade level, and general average indicate students' academic background and potential influencing factors. Additionally, the frequency and methods of self-assessment practices shed light on students' engagement and proactive approach to learning. Ultimately, the framework provides a structured approach to investigating the relationship between students' characteristics, self-assessment practices, and learning/performance outcomes.

Problem Statement

The study examined the relationship between students' self-assessment practices and academic performance. It has long been a problem for students to evaluate themselves, affecting their school performance. The difficulty at hand centers around determining students' self-assessment and whether or not it affects their academic performance. By delving into this issue, the research sought to uncover how self-assessment can influence a student's academic performance. This research explored various dimensions of self-assessment by examining using the following questions:

- Is there a significant difference in academic performance among students of different abilities when they practice self-assessment?
- Does implementing self-assessment practices result in significant changes in students' academic performance?
- How do different self-assessment methods influence students' academic performance?

The answers to these questions help educators understand the impact of self-assessment on student learning outcomes and guide the development of teaching strategies that promote effective self-assessment practices.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between student self-assessment practices and academic performance.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study examined the relationship between student self-assessment practices and academic performance in a high school setting. The research focused on 100 students at a high school in Negros Oriental, providing a representative sample of the student body. The analysis covered an entire academic year, allowing for a comprehensive observation of the impact of self-assessment practices over time. The research setting was limited to a single high school, offering a consistent data collection and analysis environment. The study utilized a quantitative approach, gathering data from surveys, academic records, and performance assessments. The independent variables in this study are student self-assessment practices, while the dependent variable is academic performance, measured through grades, test scores, and other academic indicators. Although this study aimed to understand the link between self-assessment and academic performance, there are some limitations to consider. First, the study occurred in just one high school, which might not reflect what happens in other schools or different areas. With a sample size of 100 students, it might cover less variety seen in other schools or educational settings. The school's unique aspects—like its teaching style, culture, or student background—could also impact the results. Because of these limitations, the findings might not apply to other schools or places. Future research would need to include more schools and a bigger group of students to get a broader picture.

Literature Review

The Role of Self-assessment in Learning

Self-assessment activities help students to be realistic in judging their performance and improving their work (Cornell University, 2024). Education aims to produce critical thinkers who can evaluate and analyze different information gathered in their chosen field of expertise (Boud, 2022). Contemporary approaches emphasize the active engagement of students in their learning, learner responsibility, meta-cognitive skills, and a dialogical, collaborative learning model (Spiller, 2019). Self-assessment is a significant learning component because the student gathers information and reflects on his learning. It enhances the potential of learner development as a lifelong learner (Boud, 2022). Keeping these things in mind, the present study was planned to assess the impact of self-assessment by medical students on their subsequent academic performance (Rajeev Sharma et al., 2016). When students employ self-assessment tactics, they become more invested in the progress, facilitating interest in assessing data. Tracking progress can become a competition with oneself while identifying gaps in learning becomes more accessible due to interest in improvement and attentive focus, which often accompany self-assessment (Andrade, 2019). A rubric can help identify strengths and weaknesses and introduce students to receiving constructive criticism. Sharing checklists can also help students track their progress and data (Ndoye, 2017). To ensure the students understand the instructions, they must be voiced over more than twice and written down for everyone to see or handed out separately to each student (Crooks et al., 2020).

The Impact of Self-assessment on Academic Results

Self-assessment can enhance learning outcomes when implemented for formative purposes, so it has received considerable attention in higher education (Sitzmann et al., 2010). An increasing number of empirical studies investigating the effect of self-assessment on academic performance have emerged. However, there needs to be a current meta-analytical synthesis of

the findings; most recent meta-analyses of the effect of self-assessment on academic performance were all in the K-12 context (Youde, 2019). In addition, there needs to be a significant gap in understanding how to design effective self-assessment interventions. Self-assessment could be an implicit process without observable external evidence. A theoretical claim is that self-assessment should be made explicit, i.e., self-assessment actions should be observable or traceable, to enact their potential pedagogical and practical advantages (Nicol & McCallum, 2021) because it is only with traceable actions that teachers can monitor the process and design interventions to improve their quality. As self-assessment requires students to evaluate their work, it could be an implicit process, as it happens in one's head without observable evidence (Zi et al., 2021).

Self-assessment Tools and Techniques

Varying techniques have been used and created to encourage students to participate in self-assessment practices. These techniques include, but are not limited to, teacher knowledge, feedback from peers or teachers, rubrics, and the use of master examples. A teacher will facilitate and model self-assessment techniques to encourage student engagement. Teachers do not have to implement self-assessment techniques for every learning intention and lesson. However, it is essential to encourage students to use self-assessment strategies to have the opportunity to be self-regulated learners. When creating self-assessment strategies in an educational setting, educators must engage in learning intentions and success criteria within a given standard, along with reviewing educational standards set by the state. Learning intentions and success criteria should be engaged before an educator can create a lesson plan. A learning intention should first be created, and then success criteria will follow to support assessing student understanding (Grafwallner, 2019). Rubrics have been commonly used in the educational setting for multiple reasons. However, in self-assessment, students use rubrics, and teachers model them to encourage reflection. For rubrics to be effectively used with self-assessment, they must be simplified and clearly explained before students use them (Deehan, 2016). The simplification of a rubric should be in terms that a student should understand and apply to content matter. Once a rubric is created, a teacher should model how to engage with the tool in a particular subject matter (Fisher et al., 2017). Feedback from peers and teachers is usually encouraged in a classroom setting. Collaboration techniques should be implemented in the classroom to encourage feedback from multiple sources (Fletcher, 2019). When working with a given standard, learning intention, or success criteria, opportunities for collaboration should be encouraged. Collaboration on a content standard incites feedback from teachers and peers (Fletcher, 2019). With feedback, peer critiques are often used to encourage student self-assessment. Critiquing aims to help students improve in content areas (Minero, 2016). Along with students engaging with one another, teachers should constantly provide feedback to their students to be made aware of their progress in their learning. For students to begin self-assessing their work, teachers should set a standard and provide examples of what the benchmark should look like. Examples can be collected from a teacher's work, previous students, or outside sources (Minero, 2016). An example for self-assessment purposes is an essay previously written by a student to show current peers what the goal should be.

Educator Involvement and Guidance with Techniques

For self-assessment to be successful, it needs to be directed by a teacher and paired with techniques for implementation. According to Tileston et al. (2004), student self-assessment is the most underused form of classroom assessment. For self-assessment to be implemented,

strategies must be defined to create student success. According to Vagle et al. (2018), the desire to have students invest in their learning is ubiquitous, but creating the conditions and providing consistent opportunities for students to be fully invested from the start may meet with varying levels of success. Instructional maneuvers within the context of ongoing instruction provide rich opportunities to help students develop confidence and the ability to self-assess. For self-assessment to be successful, classroom conditions need to be established for a sense of shared responsibility (Vagle et al., 2018). Along with student self-assessment strategies, it was noted that instruction plays a valuable role in self-understanding (Elder, 2010). The success of student self-assessment is achieved through three conditions that create a bridge between where the students currently are and where they need to be. These conditions allow the transfer of responsibility from teacher to student (Vagle et al., 2018). The first condition is called clear learning intentions. Clear learning intentions are for students and teachers to understand the educational experience. Learning intentions are a statement of what a student is supposed to learn about in a lesson (Fisher et al., 2017). For learning intentions to be inviting and engaging, they must be worded positively and to the needs of the students, along with the promotion of a growth mindset (Fisher et al., 2017). Hattie (2009) promotes learning intentions as “the sense that all (teachers and students) are working toward positive learning gains” (p. 103). Self-assessment can begin when the learning experience is clarified (Vagle et al., 2018). The second condition is clear success criteria. Clear success criteria are from the pre-learning experience, where students demonstrate a proficient understanding of the learning process (Vagle et al., 2018). Learning intentions and success criteria are both needed to change a learning environment; both have been proven to increase students’ internal motivation (Fisher et al., 2017). Success criteria are strategies for students to participate they learned actively and strategies for assessing themselves along the way (Fisher et al., 2017). The success criteria will let the student know what the student will learn and how a student can show the learning. The third condition is for a clear interpretation of criteria. Students must be able to interpret the success criteria. Overall, educators will start with the learning intention and break that down into success criteria. The interpretation of that success criteria to promote student success must be broken down into three questions. "What am I learning? Why am I learning this? How will I know I have learned it?" (Almarode et al., 2020, p. 34). Teachers can implement a practice of a certain standard within the learning environment and see examples for students to meet the target (Vagle et al., 2018).

Challenges and Limitations of Self-assessment

Because the research behind the implementation of self-assessment in classrooms is so new, there needs to be more data supporting whether there is a significant positive link between self-assessment and student success (Kostons et al., 2009). In addition to the limited number of studies performed, most studies have only involved relatively small sample sizes of students at a time (Panadero & Courtney, 2014). Of the research that did find significant links between the use of self-assessment and academic achievement, many postulate that students may not benefit from self-assessment because they cannot accurately use the tools and strategies to assess themselves (Kostons et al., 2009, 2012). This is especially true for students still in their adolescence who do not possess the cognitive maturity to monitor themselves. Kostons et al. Describe adolescents’ cognitive functioning as limiting, making it difficult for students to focus on assessing themselves and the process of learning concurrently without getting distracted. Many studies have found that when students are allowed to assess their work, the results of their assessments depend on whether the assignments contribute to their grades (Ross, 2006; Panadero et al., 2014; Kostons et al., 2009). The consensus is that students are likelier to

overestimate their abilities and achievement when the assessments are part of their grades (Ross, 2006; Panadero et al., 2014; Kostons et al., 2009). This is one of the most significant setbacks of first trying to implement self-assessment into the classroom because it deviates away from the original purpose of self-assessment, which is to provide the students with an idea of their learning progress and allow for the improvement of achievement of learning outcomes rather than serve as an ending point for their learning (MacMillan & Hearn, 2008). An additional result of student over-estimation of achievement level is that students may lose motivation over time if the actual results of their learning do not match with what they perceived was their level (Ross, 2006).

Gaps in Current Knowledge and Future Directions

While the study offers valuable insights into how these two elements are connected, several gaps require further exploration. Identifying these gaps is critical to guiding future research and improving educational practices. One significant gap in the research on self-assessment practices and academic performance is the need for more understanding of the long-term impact of self-assessment on students' academic trajectories (Calinescu, 2023). While many studies, including ours, examine the short-term benefits of self-assessment—such as improved student engagement or immediate test performance—there is little information on how self-assessment practices influence academic success over time. To address this gap, future research should focus on longitudinal studies that track students who engage in self-assessment throughout their educational journey. This approach would help determine whether consistent self-assessment contributes to sustained academic growth, better knowledge retention, and enhanced critical thinking skills. Additionally, such studies could reveal how self-assessment practices evolve as students advance through different educational levels, offering insights into how these practices might be optimized to support lifelong learning. By filling this gap, researchers can better understand the enduring effects of self-assessment and provide educators with evidence-based strategies for integrating self-assessment into educational systems to promote long-term student success. Global education issues include the utilization of technology in the classroom, equal access to high-quality education, and the understanding of the effect of socioeconomic level on student performance (Cariaga et al., 2024). Aseñas et al. (2023) emphasize the growing importance of digital literacy. Particularly in underdeveloped rural locations, regional schools—especially those in poor rural communities—may find challenges in reading and math. Research done in the Philippines suggests that parental participation shapes children's reading and numeracy skills. Less in-person encounters throughout the epidemic have highlighted the mathematical anxiety and resilience of affected youngsters. Because psychological and academic performance are correlated, students need tailored mentorship to fit online learning (Ginoo et al., 2023). As a possible answer to educational difficulties, Moroccans are considering the use of social entrepreneurship education (Halaissi et al., 2023). In the end, this strategy helps pupils to cooperate on tasks, thereby benefiting society. These studies however leave a great knowledge vacuum on the connection between academic performance and self-assessment strategies. Little is known about the possibility of self-evaluation to build individuals' capacity and increase their academic performance, even if most current studies focus on traditional assessment techniques and their consequences on student results. Gerodias (2024) claimed that employing self-regulated learning and self-assessment tools in remote and hybrid learning environments can significantly affect student performance in 2024. Examining the relationship between students and their academic performance will help one to get important understanding of how one may use their capacity for self-assessment to increase their performance (Cariaga et al., 2024; Estrella, 2024).

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study is descriptivecorrelational. This approach allows the exploration of the relationship between student self-assessment practices and academic performance without manipulating variables. The goal is to identify patterns and connections between these key areas, which can inform further studies and educational practices. An online survey was used to collect data. This method allowed for efficient distribution and response collection, reaching a broader audience with minimal physical contact.

Locale of the Study

The locale of this study focuses on students within the geographical parameter of Negros Island. The study used an online environment to reach the respondents, allowing for flexibility and a broader reach. By distributing the survey through Facebook and Google Forms, the study was able to engage with students from various schools and educational backgrounds across the island. This online approach provided an efficient way to gather data without being limited to a specific physical location. The use of digital platforms like Facebook and Google Forms ensured that a diverse range of students could participate in the study, contributing to a richer dataset and a broader understanding of the research topic.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents for this study were students chosen through a random sampling technique. The survey was distributed via social media, Messenger, and email to reach various respondents. This approach helped to ensure that a diverse group of students had an opportunity to participate in the study. An online survey tool was used to collect responses, allowing for electronic submission without needing a physical location. Using a random sampling technique meant that every student in the target population had an equal chance of being included in the survey, reducing the risk of bias and contributing to more reliable results.

Sampling Technique

A random sampling technique was used to select the 30 respondents for this study. This method ensured that each student in the senior high schools had an equal chance of being included in the sample, thereby reducing potential bias. Random sampling also helps achieve a representative sample, enhancing the study's reliability and generalizability of its results.

Data Gathering Instrument

The primary data-gathering instrument was a questionnaire designed specifically for this study. The questionnaire included multiple-choice and open-ended questions to gather comprehensive information on self-assessment practices and academic performance. It covered aspects such as the frequency and types of self-assessment activities and self reported academic outcomes, including grades and other indicators of academic success.

Validity and Reliability

Educational experts thoroughly reviewed the questionnaire to ensure its validity and reliability. This review ensured that the questions were clear, relevant, and aligned with the study's objectives. A pilot test with a smaller group of students was conducted to identify any issues with the questionnaire, such as unclear questions or potential misinterpretations.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure involved several vital steps. First, permission was obtained from the school's administration to conduct the study with the Senior High Department students. Once approved, the questionnaires were distributed to the selected respondents, and clear instructions were given on how to complete them. Students were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and that the information would be used solely for research purposes. The completed questionnaires were collected, and the data was analyzed to explore the relationship between student self-assessment practices and academic performance.

Ethical Considerations

Personal information obtained from the respondents—including academic records and self-assessment responses—was kept private under anonymity and confidence. Anonymity was preserved throughout the study; the final report or shared with unauthorized persons revealed no identifiable information. The study was designed to ensure respondents neither suffered physically nor emotionally. Great care was taken to prevent detrimental impacts on students' academic desire and self-esteem, especially for those who could have struggled with their performance. The researchers faithfully entered their data and findings. Bias was avoided, and data were not changed to fit a particular hypothesis, preserving the integrity of the data collection and analysis process. The researchers could freely approach the project and set its objectives. Every element of the study could be looked at to ensure adherence to moral research standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, illustrating their characteristics using mean and percentage frequency. In terms of sex, the data indicates that ten respondents (33.3%) were male, while 20 respondents (66.7%) were female, suggesting a higher representation of female participants in the study. Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents, comprising 16 individuals (53.3%), were in Grade 11, followed by seven respondents (23.3%) in Grade 12 and another 7 (23.3%) in college. This distribution highlights the predominant presence of Grade 11 students in the sample. Furthermore, regarding occupation, 26 respondents (87.0%) identified themselves as students, while four respondents (13.0%) indicated they were working students, indicating that most participants primarily engaged in academic pursuits.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

		Frequency Count	Percentage Distribution
Sex	Male	10	33.3
	Female	20	66.7
Highest educational attainment	Grade 11	16	53.3
	Grade 12	7	23.3
	College	7	23.3
Occupation	Student	26	87.0
	Working-student	4	13.0
TOTAL		30.0	100.0

The Extent of the Self-assessment and Academic Performance of Students

Table 2 presents the extent to which self-assessment practices impact academic performance among students. The mean scores, ranging from 3.05 to 3.65, reflect respondents' perceptions of the correlation between self-assessment and academic outcomes. A mean score of 3.05 suggests a moderate correlation, while scores closer to 3.65 indicate a very high extent. Respondents strongly agree or agree that self-assessment enhances interest, motivation, and learning outcomes, contributing positively to academic performance. Overall, the table provides insights into the perceived influence of self-assessment on students' academic success.

Table 2. Mean of the Indicators in the Self-assessment and Academic Performance of Students

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Students who believe they perform well academically tend to have higher grades.	3.05	Moderate extent of correlation.
Self-assessment boosts interest and motivation, enhancing academic performance.	3.53	High extent of benefit.
Self-assessment improves learning outcomes.	3.65	Very high extent of improvement.
Total	3.41	Moderate to high extent of positive impact on academic performance.

The Extent of the Learning Activities

Table 3 presents the mean scores and interpretations for statements regarding various learning activities and their impact on academic success. The mean scores, ranging from 2.75 to 3.73, reflect respondents' perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of these activities. Higher mean scores suggest a stronger belief or agreement in the statements presented. For instance, respondents strongly agree or agree that self-assessment practices inform teaching and learning practices (mean = 3.73), indicating a high extent of belief in the role of self-assessment in enhancing academic achievement. Conversely, lower mean scores, such as for the statement about the measurement of academic performance (mean = 2.75), suggest a more moderate level of agreement among respondents. Overall, the table provides insights into the perceived relationship between learning activities and academic success among students, highlighting areas of consensus and potential areas for further exploration.

Table 3. Mean of the Indicators in the Learning Activities

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Students with a high opinion of themselves when it comes to learning will be successful in the future.	3.58	High extent of belief in self-efficacy.
Academic performance can ensure a successful future.	3.27	Moderate extent
The relationship between self-assessment and academic achievement can inform teaching and learning practices.	3.73	High extent
Academic performance could be measured through various indicators.	2.75	Moderate extent
The student can comply with all the activities, and it is achievable.	2.78	Moderate extent
Total	3.222	Moderate to high extent of positive impact on academic performance.

The Extent of the Relationship Between Student Self-Assessment and Academic Success

Table 4 presents the mean scores and interpretations for statements regarding the relationship between student self-assessment practices and academic success. The mean scores, ranging from 3.23 to 4.00, reflect the extent of belief among respondents in the impact of self-assessment on academic outcomes. Higher mean scores suggest a stronger belief in the positive

influence of self-assessment, while lower scores indicate a more moderate level of belief. For instance, respondents strongly agree that self-assessment can help build confidence, improve academic performance, and contribute to a deeper understanding of academic concepts. Conversely, there is a more moderate belief regarding the sufficiency of self-assessment alone for achieving better grades. Overall, the table provides insights into the perceived relationship between student self-assessment and academic success, highlighting areas of solid consensus and potential areas for further investigation.

Table 4. The Relationship Between Student Self-Assessment and Academic Success

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Self-assessment can help students build confidence and improve academic performance.	4.00	Very high confidence
There will be a positive correlation between students' self-assessments and academic achievements.	3.27	High extent
Student self-assessment contributes to a deeper understanding of academic concepts.	3.73	The very great extent in self-assessment.
Student self-assessment enhances learning outcomes and academic success.	2.75	Very high extent in self-assessment's positive impact on outcomes and success.
Self-assessments are sufficient for learners to achieve better grades.	2.78	Moderate extent in self-assessment's sufficiency for grade improvement.
Total	3.20	High to very high extent of success.

The Extent of the Health Safety

Table 5 presents the mean scores and interpretations for statements related to the influence of self-assessment on academic performance in health safety. The mean scores, ranging from 3.85 to 4.00, indicate a high to very high extent of belief among respondents in the positive impact of self-assessment on health safety education. Respondents strongly agree or agree that self-assessment activities positively influence academic performance and foster a culture of continuous learning and improvement. Additionally, respondents have a consensus regarding the importance of student self-assessment in ensuring health and safety practices.

Table 5. Mean of the Indicators in Health Safety

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Self-assessment positively influences academic performance and health safety.	3.85	High extent
Self-assessment fosters continuous learning and improvement in health safety education.	3.87	High Extent
Student self-assessment is essential for ensuring health and safety practices.	4.00	Very high extent
Total	3.91	High to very high belief in the relationship between self-assessment and health safety in academic performance.

The study's findings reveal a demographic profile of 10 male and 20 female respondents, indicating a higher representation of females at 66.7% compared to males at 33.3%. Regarding educational attainment, most respondents, accounting for 53.3%, were in Grade 11, 23.3% in Grade 12, and 23.3% already enrolled in college. Furthermore, the occupational status of the respondents showed that the majority (87.0%) identified themselves as students, with a smaller proportion (13.0%) indicating that they were working students. These findings offer valuable insights into the composition of the study participants, shedding light on their gender distribution, educational levels, and occupational backgrounds.

The Relationship between Students' self-assessment practices and academic achievement

Table 6 shows results for elements related to students' self-assessment, relationship with academic success and health safety practices. Every one of the four p-values is below the approved 0.05 threshold, so the null hypothesis (H_0) rejection for each one of them reveals the statistical importance of the variables in their relationship to student performance and health safety. With a p-value of 0.045, the chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 3.85$ shows that academic performance as well as health safety are much positively influenced by self-assessment. This outcome underlines the significance of self-assessment as a tool that enables students evaluate their academic growth and make necessary modifications as well as raises their awareness and adherence to health and safety measures. Based on a chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 2.87$ and a p-value of 0.049, this research especially in the framework of health safety education reveals that self-assessment considerably encourages continuous learning and improvement. This underlines the importance of self-assessment as a necessary feedback mechanism wherein students may monitor their improvement in understanding of health and safety concerns and constantly

improve their application of these principles. Correct health and safety practices rely on self-assessment according to a chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 4.00$ and a p-value of 0.034. This result supports the hypothesis that regular self-assessment of students raises their probability of adopting responsibility for their health and safety, therefore enhancing adherence to safety practices. Meanwhile, the chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 4.00$ and the p-value of 0.049 provide a final result that is similar to the first variable, therefore verifying that self-assessment has a main positive influence on both academic performance and health safety. This consistency underscores even more the significance of adding self-assessment into the learning process because it not only improves academic performance but also encourages safer behaviors. The findings of all four factors imply that self-assessment is quite important for both raising academic performance and promoting health safety practices. These results suggest that encouraging students to engage in regular self-assessment might be a good strategy to improve outcomes connected to their health as well as their academics.

Table 6. The Relationship between Students' self-assessment practices and academic achievement

Variables Correlated to Students' Practices and Performance	χ^2	p-value	Decision	Remark
Performance				
Self-assessment positively influences academic performance and health safety.	3.85	0.045	reject H_{01}	significant
Self-assessment fosters continuous learning and improvement in health safety education.	3.87	0.049	reject H_{01}	significant
Student self-assessment is essential for ensuring health and safety practices.	4.00	0.034	reject H_{01}	significant
Self-assessment positively influences academic performance and health safety.	4.00	0.049	reject H_{01}	significant

Summary of Findings

The study examined students' opinions of themselves and their academic performance after graduation. The following items rank highest among the most crucial: Students will generally do well in life if they like to perform well in school. More often than not, students who engaged

in this behaved better in the classroom than those who did not. Self-evaluation has been demonstrated to improve individuals' metacognitive abilities. The students performed better in the classroom as they understood their learning style, current ability level, and areas for improvement. Students with better self-control were found to be more emotionally under control. This was good for the classroom, as they better scheduled their time, tracked themselves, and created objectives, all skills needed to excel. Students who answered a self-test claimed to be more driven to perform well in the classroom and to have changed interests. Self-evaluation might enable individuals to get more engaged and ready to learn. Different forms of self-evaluation—such as reflection diaries, group reports, and rubrics—make students either perform better or worse in the classroom. According to studies, including this one, these approaches to instruction are best suited when combined. The statistics showed that when you are honest with yourself, you should consult a master. Adults should teach teenagers how to assess themselves and provide comments to enable them to do it properly. Giving teenagers self-evaluation projects in the classroom has been shown to help them perform better and impart valuable skills that will enable them to study for their lifetime. However, more study is needed to ascertain the long-term consequences of self-evaluation and whether it applies in every educational environment.

Conclusion

There is a definite relationship found between students' use of self-assessment techniques and their academic achievement. The study came to the conclusion that achieving great academic achievement, actively participating in education, and self-evaluation are all essential for the development of metacognitive capacity. The study's shortcomings were mostly caused by its narrow focus, which only included graduates of a certain high school. However, it emphasized how crucial it is to do more study in other educational settings in order to confirm the validity of the conclusions. Teachers may include well-thought-out projects for students to review themselves in their lesson plans to make the classroom a busier place to learn. They would then help their students set reasonable learning goals, be honest about their skills, and know they are in charge of their future academic success. As time passes, schools should try various self-evaluation tools and methods, as well as how self-evaluation affects students' long-term academic progress. The best ways to use self-evaluation to improve learning and do well in school will become clear as you keep working on this project. Further research in this area is crucial to uncover the most effective ways to use self-evaluation to support students in their academic journey. Educators and researchers play a vital role in this process, and their continued efforts will be instrumental in enhancing student learning and success.

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